

WHEN THE GAVEL FALLS SHORT: GAPS IN LAW AND THE QUEST FOR REFORM.

**By Sunday Otseanya Theresa, SobowaleAnuoluwapoKehinde., AdeosunDolapoChristianah.,
Oluwatimilehin Amos Oluwatoyosi.**

ABSTRACT

A major challenge within the Nigerian legal system is the existence of significant lacuna areas, where legal provisions are absent, outdated or inadequate to address certain issues. These gaps weaken the effectiveness of the law, hinder justice and contribute to the fault found in the society. This article critically examines the lacunas present in five key areas in Nigeria Legal System, which are Criminal law, Family and Inheritance law, Labour and Employment Law, Constitutional and Human Rights Law and Environmental Law. It explore how these laws affect the society and how they contribute to injustice. With reference to case laws, provisions from Acts and statutes and also legal scholars, the article highlighted the urgent need for reform to the bridge of these gaps. By proposing targeted reforms, it advocates for an effective legal system capable of addressing these laws and their importance.

This article delves into the consequences of lacunas in our laws, stating few areas that needs to be refreshed, and also how these gaps lead to continuous injustice, confusion and inequality. It also argues that until these gaps are bridged and looked into through reforms, the promise of justice remains incomplete.

INTRODUCTION

A true life story makes this injustice painfully clear; a young undergraduate, attending a night reading session on campus was sexually assaulted by five female cultists who were armed with weapons. He was threatened and overpowered, he endured a harrowing violation, but when justice was supposed to prevail, when it was supposed to be felt like winning a trophy, it wasn't however, the law was silent.

Under the criminal code, there is a clause in the definition of rape that a man cannot be raped. Due to this clause a man raped is left alone all by himself without a pathway to accountability, he is faced not only with trauma and stigma, but also a legal system that refused to acknowledge his pain.

In every part of Nigeria, people are faced with the same issue. Their stories differ but their results are similar, the law is absent. As the saying goes; *"where there is no law, there is no wrong"* and if a tortious act occurs but is not provided by the law who bears the fault? Not the law itself or the court but the victim, the masses. Criminal acts not recognized as crimes under the law is no crime and would not be addressed in Court. When the law fails to evolve or address emerging realities, it leaves gaps which lead to justice being delayed, denied or distorted.

A Lacuna is a Latin word which means "pit or hole", it refers to those silent spaces where no law applies, or where existing laws are vague or in conflict. These gaps not only affect the society, but also affect the trust and faith the people have in the legal system.

²¹¹GAPS / SILENCE IN CRIMINAL LAW

Criminal law is a codified set of rules that defines, regulates, and controls behaviors deemed criminal within a society. ¹ It serves as a shield for society, protecting individuals by punishing offenders and maintaining public order. However, Nigerian criminal law is silent on certain offences and often fails to

²¹¹1. D. J. Sagay, Adekeye (Eds), Perspectives on Nigerian Law and Society (Princeton Publishing 2019) 143.

2. Olusegun Adekoya (ed), Perspectives on Nigerian Laws and Society (Princeton Publishing 2019) 143.

3. Criminal Code Act, Cap C38, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

4. Criminal Code Act, s 357.

5. Victoria Ayeni, 'The Inadequacies of Nigerian Criminal Law in Protecting Male Rape Victims' (2021) Nigerian Journal of Criminal Justice Reform.

6. Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act, 2015.

keep up with modern realities. This silence/gaps results not only in the delay of justice but in its absolute denial. In Nigeria, various gaps in the criminal justice system have left victims powerless, helpless, and unprotected, while encouraging offenders to act without fear of punishment or consequences of their actions, thereby disregarding the law without repercussions. These gaps, therefore, expose the limits of our legal protections and point the urgent need for change (reform).²

One of the most noticeable examples of this legal silence is the treatment of male rape victims. The Criminal Code Act³ restricts the definition of rape to acts committed by a man against a woman, thereby excluding male victims from full legal protection (Section 357 Criminal Code)⁴. This definition concentrates rape as an act against a woman, leaving no room for the experiences of male victims. Such a restricted or limited perspective neglects to recognize that men and boys can also be victims of sexual violence, completely leaving them without appropriate legal remedies. Researchers have argued that this blatant gap is seen as a reflection of outdated gender assumptions entrenched in Nigerian law.⁵

Another critical area where Nigeria's criminal law falls short is in its treatment of emerging cybercrimes. Though the Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act, 2015⁶ was enacted to regulate online offences, it has not kept pace with advancing digital threats such as revenge pornography, cyberstalking, and online sexual harassment. Many of these crimes, particularly those affecting young people and women, do not fit neatly into traditional categories of criminal law. Because the law has not advanced alongside technology, victims often lack sufficient²¹² protection, and perpetrators act without fear of liability. Scholars have pointed out that despite the potency of the digital world to modern Nigerian life, it remains inadequately regulated.⁷

The escalating impact of these lacunae is a criminal justice system that selectively protects certain victims while ignoring others. When the law fails to recognize male rape or adequately address cybercrimes, it sends a dangerous message: that some harms are invisible, or worse, unworthy of redress.

In 2020, a Nigerian woman fell victim to revenge pornography when her private photos were maliciously circulated online by an ex-boyfriend. Regardless of the existence of the Cybercrimes Act,

7. Abdullahi Musa, 'Emerging Cybercrimes and the Legal Challenges in Nigeria' (2020) African Journal of Law and Technology.

8. ChuksEzeani, *Legal Evolution and the Protection of Vulnerable Groups* (Lagos Justice Press 2020) 78.

9. 'Nigerian Woman Seeks Justice After Ex-Boyfriend Leaks Private Photos Online', Premium Times (12 March 2020).

procedural loopholes and definitional ambiguities prevented her from obtaining swift justice, because when legal systems fail to evolve, they leave victims exposed, embolden offenders, and undermine public trust in justice.⁸

*"As Ezeani rightly observes, a legal system that fails to adapt to emerging realities ultimately fails those it is meant to protect."*⁹Victims who find no remedy within the formal legal framework may lose faith in the justice system altogether, resulting in a rise in instances of self-help, vigilantism, and social unrest. When the law proves inadequate, the consequences ripple far beyond individual cases, eroding the very fabric of public trust.

In sum, the gaps within Nigeria's criminal law, whether in addressing male rape or confronting emerging cybercrimes pinpoint a system in crucial demand for change. Without intentional legislative action to close these lacunae, injustice will persist and the credibility of the justice system will continue to erode. Strengthening the law to protect all categories of victims is not only a legal necessity; it is a public necessity (a fundamental must-do).

²¹³ GAPS IN FAMILY AND INHERITANCE LAW.

Family and inheritance law are laws guiding the family and inheritance of the members of the family, which are governed by a blend of statutory law, customary laws and Islamic laws. However, there are some areas in the law which can be referred to as lacunas in the law and these areas affect the people it was supposed to protect such as women, children, etc. These gaps can be in form of conflicts between the customary and statutory law in marriage, child custody and succession, can be the provision of gender bias and legal uncertainty in the laws or forum shopping and inconsistent Judicial outcomes.

CONFLICTS EXISTING BETWEEN CUSTOMARY AND STATUTORY LAW IN MARRIAGE, CHILD CUSTODY AND SUCCESSION.

Marriage is a legally and socially recognized union between two individuals, involving a formal ceremony and often a legal contract, creating a bond that establishes rights and obligations between the spouses, as well as between them and any children they may have. In other words, it is the state of being united as spouses in a consensual and contractual relationship recognized by law.

Conflicts exist between statutory and customary law which causes confusion as to the validity of the

10 (1866) LR 1 PD 130

11 Child Rights Act of 2003

marriage. Statutory laws only recognizes monogamous marriage as seen in **Hyde v. Hyde**.¹⁰ Meanwhile, customary law gives room for polygamous marriages which causes complications with inheritance, property rights and the legal status of the spouses and children. For a marriage to be valid under the statute, it must be between persons of marriageable age, however customary law permits marriage between persons of younger age (especially the female gender). Some couples may contract both statutory and customary marriages and this causes confusion on which law the marriage is contracted on. It can be simply put that English or statutory marriages are monogamous while customary marriages are polygamous.

Conflicts between both laws also exist in the determination the child's custody, In Nigeria, statutory marriages (legally registered under the Matrimonial Causes Act) grant both parents equalrights to custody, and the court will consider the best interest of the child in making its decision. The Child Rights Act of 2003¹¹ also plays an important role in ensuring the child's well-being. In²¹⁴ customary marriages, the father often has a right to custody, without the best interest of the child being considered. This can create a conflict with the provisions of statutory law, as the court may need to balance the child's wellbeing and welfare with customary practices. Also in succession, customary law allows only male children to inherit the properties of the father, while the female children are not given a right to inherit the property of their father. In **Ukeje v. Ukeje**¹², There was a conflict between the statutory law and customary law on her inheritance rights, she had to fight for her rights to inherit the properties of her father which abolished the Igbo customary law that excluded women from such inheritance.

GENDER BIAS AND LEGAL UNCERTAINTY

Gender bias is an important issue that affects almost every aspect of our society. It affects decisions made in the workplace, the opportunities available to individuals, and even how people relate with each other¹³. This affects women's inheritance rights, especially in cultures where customary laws prevail.

A woman who marries under customary or Islamic law in Nigeria does not enjoy adequate legal protection in the distribution of assets. Under customary arrangement, the husband is generally regarded as having dominant power to dispose of family property. In some cases, this power is often exercised

12 (2014) LPELR-22724(SC)

13 Understanding gender bias key issues and strategies for change. April 2023.

14 MujibatOshodi. The inheritance rights of women in Nigeria. 7 Nov, 2023.

15 (2014) LPELR-22724(SC)

without paying attention to the wife's, contributions as assets are usually acquired in the husband's name,¹⁴ i.e. English or statutory inheritance rules enunciate the principle of equality while customary rules promote gender bias. As provided in **Ukeje v. Ukeje**¹⁵ whose rights would have been trampled upon because of her gender if not for her standing up to the Igbo customary law and fighting for her rights.

²¹⁵**FORUM SHOPPING AND UNCERTAIN JUDICIAL OUTCOMES**

Forum shopping refers to the practice of selecting the most favorable jurisdiction or court for initiating legal action. Generally, forum shopping is deemed to have negative impact, as it is portrayed as a strategy to choose a jurisdiction for its favourable substantive law or to avoid unfavorable procedural laws in another forum (for example, selecting a specific jurisdiction can impose significant financial burdens on the opposing party or influence the evidentiary regime by expanding or limiting the range of admissible evidence). Learned Scholars also see it as a way of gaining illegitimate advantages or higher compensation.¹⁶ Forum shopping and inconsistent Judicial outcomes has affected the society in a negative way rather than a positive way, because parties with higher capacity can choose which court they go to, and most times, the inconsistent Judicial outcomes give rise to apathy among people, mostly people who feel the rich and powerful usually have their way.

²¹⁶**LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT LAW**

Labour and employment laws are the laws that govern the relationship between employers and employees. It mediates the relationship between worker, employing entities, trade unions, and the government.

Labour and employment law can be defined as a dynamic field that reflects the changing socio-economic environment, balancing the power relations between employers and employees, and serving as an instrument for social justice and economic development.¹⁷

The various laws that guide this field are Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria 1999(as amended), Labor Act Cap L1, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004, Trade Unions Act, etc.

¹⁶ Forum shopping, a legal loophole or a strategic advantage? A glance at the Italian experience. Friday, 4 April, 2025.

¹⁷ Nigerian association of Law Teachers, Proceedings of the 51st Annual Conference of the Nigerian Association of Law Teachers (NALT 2018), p. 87.

¹⁸ Labour Act Cap L1, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004, s.91

The main aim of these laws is to guarantee that the rights of workers/employees are protected.

LACUNAS IN LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT LAW

k. Labour and Employment Laws Are Not Unified and They Have Weak Enforcement

So many laws guide different aspects of labour and employment law which leads to fragmentation and confusion. These fragmented laws are difficult to enforce due to bureaucracy, therefore there is no point in having such laws if it cannot be enforced properly.

1. The limited definition of “worker”

“worker” according to Section 91 of the Labour Act¹⁸ can be defined as ‘any person who has entered into or works under a contract with an employer, whether the contract is for manual labour or clerical work or is expressed or implied or oral or written and whether it is a contract of service or a contract personally to execute any work or labour’. This section exempts professional workers, administrative workers, etc., from enjoying these statutory provisions. These laws have little to no provisions protecting contract workers, which leads to job insecurity and exploitation.

²¹⁷GAPS IN CONSTITUTIONAL AND HUMAN RIGHT LAW

1999 Constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria is the Grund norm of all Nigeria's laws.²⁴ Other Nigeria laws derive legitimacy and recognition from this law to the extent that any law that is inconsistent with this law shall to the extent of its inconsistency be void.²⁵

Chapter IV of the 1999 constitution contains the fundamental human rights of people living in Nigeria. Fundamental human rights are not absolute as they have limitations to their exercise. It is an inherent and essential right of persons and serves to protect the dignity of humans. In recognition of this, 1999 constitution embedded the rights that are fundamental to human and necessary to everyday living.

AMBIGUITY AROUND CITIZENSHIP AND INDIGNITY IN NIGERIA

The issue of distinction between citizenship and indignity in Nigeria, with respect to the enjoyment of fundamental human right and in seeking redress whenever it is breached, as embedded in the

24 1999 Constitution of The Federal Republic of Nigeria as Amended

25 Section 1(3) of 1999 Constitution of The Federal Republic of Nigeria as Amended

26 Abimbola O, Indigeneship and Citizenship in Nigeria: Myth and Reality the Journal of Pan African Studies, vol.2, no.9, March 2009.

constitution has created more problem than imagined. Chapter III of the 1999 constitution provides for who can be identified as a citizen and how it can be acquired. This is specifically stated in section 25 to 27 of the constitution. Citizenship can be by birth, registration or naturalization. Furthermore, chapter IV of the constitution provides for Fundamental Rights of Nigeria notwithstanding their ethnicity, location or place of birth. These fundamental rights are to be enjoyed without any interference and where this is breached, a proper redress to serve justice should be made available. However, it would seem that there are extraneous factors that will impede the enjoyment of these rights which include but not limited to indignity and ethnicity. For instance, section 42 which provides right to freedom from discrimination has some undertones of indignity and ethnicity. These has been a controversial term.²⁶

The issue of citizenship and indignity could further be seen in some of the provisions of 1979 constitution from which 1999 constitution emanate from. This needs to be looked at because, it seems to be the foundational basis creating issues on indigence and citizenship. For instance, in ²¹⁸order to be considered for a position or opportunity on the basis of federal character, one has to be an indigene of the state or local government concerned. Thus, in order to be qualified, there need to be evidence pointing that you belong to a community through your parents or grandparents. It follows that, inability to prove belonging to a particular ethnic or community will result in deprivation of some basic fundamental right and privilege of indigene.²⁷

SILENCE ON DIGITAL PRIVACY

The surge in increase of the use and continual development in technology, have brought about the need for collection and storage of personal data in the whole world. This will help in detecting fraud and other criminal activities.

The collection and storage of personal data pervade all spheres of life in Nigeria. This raises important questions about privacy standards in the digital age, starting with the state's handling of personal data²⁸. The question as to whether there is proper management of data becomes imminent. The outcome of improper management of personal data is that it facilitates means by which other person data can be

27 Abimbola O, Indigene ship and Citizenship in Nigeria: Myth and Reality the Journal of Pan African Studies, vol.2, no.9, March 2009.

28 AdeboyeAdegoke digital right and privacy in Nigeria the paradigm initiative July 2020

29Consttuton of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Act No. 24, 5 May 1999, <https://constituton.awngeriacom/2018/03/26/1999-constitutionwth-amendments-nigerian-consttution-hub/>

used to defraud others.

Right to privacy of citizens, their homes correspondence, telephone conversation and telegraphic communication is provided for in section 37 of the constitution⁶. However, the fundamental rights to privacy as provided for in section 37 is not absolute. It is limited by Section 45.²⁹

²¹⁹ENVIRONMENTAL LAW

Environmental laws are the laws that are aimed at protecting the environment from environmental challenges like oil spill, deforestation, desertification, waste management, climate change, etc., and also promote sustainable development. Environmental law are rules, principles that guide the efficient use of the environment.

There are various environmental laws in Nigeria and they are National Environmental Standard Regulation Enforcement Agency Act (2007), Environmental Impact Assessment Act (1992), Petroleum Industry Act (2004), Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act (1992), etc.

The basic aim of environmental law is to protect the environment and make sure it is safe to use by the present and future generations.

LACUNAS IN ENVIRONMENTAL LAW

The important areas where lacunas are present but not limited to include:

- **Poor enforcement and weak penalties**

One of the pressing issues of environmental law is the lack of proper enforcement and the weak punishments meted out to offenders. The penalties and punishments are so lenient, people would rather break these laws than follow them, most especially big corporations³⁰, as seen in section 60 of Environmental Impact Assessment Act.

- **These legislations are not codified and they have overlapping functions³¹**

All these laws guiding different environmental issues are not arranged into a systematic order and their various functions and provisions clash with one another and this leads to low effectiveness, conflicting interpretations, limited scopes and jurisdictional issues. Section 13 of

30 Okonkwo, O. T., & Okoye, C. O. (2021). 'Environmental Law and Sustainable Development in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects.' Journal of Environmental Law and Policy.

31 Etemire, U. (2015). Law and Practice on Public Participation in Environmental Matters: The Nigerian Example in Transnational Comparative Perspective.

the water resources act and section 7f of NESREA overlap in their provision for water pollution.

e. ²²⁰**Little to nonexistent public participation and awareness³²**

Environmental issues affect the populace at large; therefore, proper avenues and channels should be made for people to participate and be heard. They should be made aware about their rights and obligations under these laws.

f. **Lack of locus standi and the non-justiciability of environmental law³³**

An individual cannot institute a legal action unless he/she shows how the issues affect him/ her personally, as seen in the case of *Oronto Douglas v Shell Petroleum Development Company Ltd & Ors*³⁴, where the court held that he lacked the sufficient interest in the issue and that he had not suffered any direct damage. They can most likely be successful when they come through the angle of using chapter 4 of the constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended 2023, as seen in *Jonah Gbemre v Shell Petroleum Development Company Nig. ltd*³⁵, where the court held the actions of the respondents by flaring gas was a violation of their fundamental right to a clean environment.

Non-Governmental Organizations were given the avenue to institute proceedings by the Supreme Court as seen in the case of ^{Centrex} *for Oil Pollution Watch v NNPC*³⁶, where the court held public spirited individuals can bring action in court against public and private entity.

Section 20 of the constitution³⁷ provides the state shall protect and improve the environment and safe guard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife in Nigeria. Unfortunately, this is found in chapter 2 of the constitution, which is the non-justiciable part of the constitution, therefore, people cannot hold the government accountable if they do not protect these rights.

32Etemire, U (2015). Law and Practice on Public Participation in Environmental Matters: The Nigerian Example in Transnational Comparative perspective.

33Atsegbua, L. A., Akpotaire, V. O., &Dimowo, F.(2004). Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice

a. (1998) LPELR-CA/L/143/97

b. (2005) 6 AHRLR 152

c. (2019) 5 NWLR (PT. 1666) 518

37Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), s.20.

WHY DO THESE LACUNA PERSIST

Lacunae in Nigeria law persist due to number of factors that is not limited to complexity of our legal system, influence of customary law, and many other factors. These gaps can arise from outdated laws, inconsistencies between different legal frameworks, or the failure of laws to adequately address emerging societal issues. The following are the reasons why lacunae persist:

1 Legislative delay and inaction:

Legislative delay and inaction in enacting new laws to meet the need of evolving social world leads to numerous outdated laws thereby occasioning injustice when justice is being sought.

2 Political reluctance or controversy:

The delay by politicians or public holder for fear of backlash or controversy to issue policy or propose a bill to remedy the inadequacy of an existing law makes lacunae to persist in the country. Whereby where new areas of laws that should be explored to achieve justice will continue to dwindle down together with Nigeria legal system without any antecedent solution.

3 Inadequate public consultation or legal reform mechanism:

Another aspect that makes lacunae persist in our system is the fact that expert opinion is not accommodated. Laws are drafted and enacted without sourcing the input of expert in that particular field or area of law to be enacted. This action leads to low response and adherence by the public and low participation since it does not meet the needs and desire of the populace.

4 Judicial improvisations as a weak substitute

In the instance where there is no existing law available to prefer solution to a particular case, the judiciary can go their way to decide the case base on their own discretion and what seems will promote the spirit of law and not contrary to public order. However, when judicial authority are left to decide a case in their discretion it may lead to unpredictable outcome and sometimes inconsistent decision, which may not adequately address the issues.

In all, it is so necessary that all stake holders should rise and see to the effect that defect in our laws are being attended to and taking cognizance in drafting it to meet the present and address the issue at hand.

CONCLUSION.

The existence of gaps in Nigeria's constitution and other Acts hinders the effectiveness of justice and governance. The lacunas found in the Criminal Law, Family and Inheritance Law, Constitutional Law

etc. cause injustice in the society and leave many without clear legal protection or guidance. Addressing these gaps through various ways and means such as making provisions for it in the constitution and other laws like the Criminal and Penal Code, Matrimonial Causes Act etc., clear interpretation of vague laws by the Courts and other reforms can not only strengthen the legal system but also ensure fairness, equality and accountability in Nigeria

RECOMMENDATION

When the law fails to address important issues, the impact can be very serious in that, injustice thrives, inconsistency spreads, and over time, public trust in the legal system begin to erode⁴⁰. Rather than just pointing out these gaps, we need to take real actions to improve and modernize our laws. The gaps in the law demands a thoughtful, urgent, and organized response to keep the legal system fair, relevant and able to meet the changing needs of the public⁴¹.

One of the successful and efficient ways to tackle these gaps is through well-functioning law reform commission⁴². These bodies are responsible for taking a close look at our laws, identifying outdated or silent areas, and recommending critical changes or reforms. Effective law reform connect and collaborate with legislatures to advance laws, ensuring the law protects vulnerable groups and adjust to changing public needs often left out of traditional legal thinking⁴³This is very necessary in Nigeria, where many of outlaws are outdated and need to be altered to represent or portray current realities.

Beyond institutional frameworks, a more comprehensive and intricate decision-making is crucial. By engaging the public on proposed laws, especially the minorities, vulnerable groups, and victims, we ensure that the law speaks to the needs of everyone and promote a better decision-making process⁴⁴. Giving room for the contribution of civil society, professional groups and ordinary citizens, we do not only create better laws but also foster trust and legitimacy in the system. This helps to reveal gaps and strengthen democratic participation.

The judiciary also has an important role to play. Courts sometimes use their discretion to interpret the law in ways that addresses ambiguities and uncertainties, especially when a strict reading²²¹would to an unfair result⁴⁵. Judicial creativity, guided by principles of fairness, equity, and good conscience⁴⁶, can serve as temporary fix until lawmakers catch up. But Judges must act cautiously, making sure they do not cross the line into making laws themselves as reaching a compromise between interpretation and

45 O. J. Okonkwo, *Judicial Approach to Statutory Interpretation in Nigeria* (Spectrum Books 2011) 102.

46 See the equitable principles guiding judicial decisions, eg in *Mojekwu v Mojekwu* (1997) 7 NWLR (Pt 512) 283.

47 M. Freeman, *Comparative Law and Legal Reform* (Oxford University Press 2015) 212.

legislation is key.

There is also much we can learn from other countries. Many legal systems use regular legislative reviews, flexible judicial approaches, and broad consultation to address gaps in the law⁴⁷. By studying and adapting these best practices to fit Nigeria's context, we can craft a practical and home grown road map for changes.

Closing the gaps in Nigerian law is not just an academic debate or a lawyer's concern, it is crucial for upholding the rule of law itself. Strong reform commissions, advance law making, innovative courts and comparative learning together show us the way forward. Amending or altering these gaps or lacuna is not just about fixing the law; it is about keeping the law alive as a true instrument of justice and not a legacy of injustice.